

SHEAR STRESS CLASSIFICATION FOR THE FINITE ELEMENT ANALYSIS OF HIP IMPLANT SURFACE TOPOGRAPHIES

Aleksandra Vulović^{1,2}, Tijana Šušteršič^{1,2}, Nenad Filipović^{1,2}

¹ Faculty of Engineering, University of Kragujevac, Sestre Janjić 6, 34000 Kragujevac, Serbia
e-mail: aleksandra.vulovic@kg.ac.rs; tijanas@kg.ac.rs; fica@kg.ac.rs

² Bioengineering Research and Development Center (BioIRC), Prvoslava Stojanovića 6,
34000 Kragujevac, Serbia

Abstract:

In order to perform numerical analysis of hip implant surface topographies several steps must be followed, such as defining model geometry values, creating a CAD model for a hip implant and femoral bone, creating a mesh for both models, defining material properties, and appropriate boundary conditions. This approach requires significant time and computational effort in order to achieve shear stress distribution for just one model, which is not enough when we are trying to find the optimal hip implant surface. A possible way to reduce time is to limit the number of models that are being analyzed using classification algorithms. The goal is to perform classification using 10 model parameters and based on the output to further analyze only models that are classified as below the threshold. Preliminary results indicate that this approach can be useful.

Keywords: classification, hip implant, surface topographies

Acknowledgement: This research is supported by the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No. 952603 - SGABU. This article reflects only the author's view. The Commission is not responsible for any use that may be made of the information it contains. The research was funded by the Ministry of Education, Science and Technological Development of the Republic of Serbia, contract number [451-03-68/2022-14/200107 (Faculty of Engineering, University of Kragujevac)].